

Oakwoods Projects East and West, Hancock County (41.02400, -83.69600)

Since construction in 2021, the Oakwoods Projects’ capacity for nutrient filtration has been limited by minimal watershed connection, resulting in little water or nutrient input to the majority of wetland pools. In 2024, even the pool intended to act as a floodplain received essentially no input, as Aurand Run did not flood sufficiently high. Additionally, tile drains connected to select pools may be clogged, limiting inputs from adjacent agricultural fields. As a result, the primary nutrient benefit of these Projects thus far has been the runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source (a combined 1.1 lbs phosphorus per acre each year). The vegetation nutrient stock at Oakwoods West Project was 413 lbs phosphorus per acre aboveground and 36 lbs phosphorus per acre belowground.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology of Oakwoods East (right) and West (left) is passively managed. Oakwoods East has 20 acres of restored wetland including four depressional pools connected to subsurface tile drains and 20 isolated depressional pools that are primarily precipitation-fed. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm in which some pools overflow and intermix. Oakwoods West has 30 acres of restored wetland including a water level control structure–equipped pool adjacent to Aurand Run that occasionally floods and 18 other depressional pools that are primarily surface runoff–fed. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm in which flow is expected to flood the pool adjacent to Aurand Run.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmland Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
50 acres	1.1 lbs	117 ± 65 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar formerly agricultural wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- While modifications may enhance Oakwoods’ connection to Aurand Run, the potential nutrient filtration benefit may be constrained by the low nutrient loads delivered by Aurand Run.
- Account for the prevention of nutrient loading from converting formerly agricultural parcels to wetlands (i.e., surface runoff and subsurface drainage prevention).
- Assess parcel for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.